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Further information on this topic: Draft outline of a Semio-Cultural Grounding Theory (SCGT) at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17459257>

What's it about?

... among other things, a fundamental problem of human existence and the question of whether a machine of a known design (e.g., so-called "AI") could replace humans. The topic is particularly relevant at the moment because "AIs" repeatedly make serious mistakes, and great efforts are therefore being made to overcome these problems. One of the biggest problems here is the so-called "grounding" problem: How do you connect a "symbol system" with the "world"?

For a "modern person," this is actually a trivial question: what you can touch is the "world." Of course, there are also things where it gets more complicated. But in principle... And it was precisely this "modern clarity" that came to an end around 1900, when Max Planck triggered the development that led to the emergence of quantum theory.

Roughly speaking, it is about the fact that there is an insurmountable boundary between the observable world and the world of the observer. The actual complexity of physical spaces cannot be completely transferred into our experiential space, since actual

physical "reality" is a high-dimensional continuum that knows no "distances" and no "distinctions." We can experience firsthand in the moment this kind of continuous reality most deeply as "resistance" because we are living beings. In order to reflect on the experience, we must make it distinguishable in time and space.

A frequently used example of this is the rainbow. In fact, its spectrum is continuous. However, we humans recognize color gradations. Without such distinctions (e.g., spatial or temporal), humans cannot consciously shape their thinking into experiences.

For many centuries, this problem was more philosophical in nature. And humanity had actually already found a vivid solution to illustrate it, namely the phrase "All good things come in threes": "There is this, there is that, and there is the other." As long as "the other" was always taken into account, it was impossible to fight to the bitter end over "this" or "that," because "the other" was always more important.

This explains the many triadic constellations found in numerous cultures around the world and is actually quite obvious when you consider that a stool is only stable if it has AT LEAST three legs. This phenomenon has to do with the following relationship, which describes the so-called reduction thesis, proposed by the American polymath Charles Sanders Peirce (1839-1914), who is considered the rediscoverer of the significance of the triad and a father of modern semiotics (including biosemiotics) and logic:

"There are relations of multiplicity 3 that cannot be generated from relations of multiplicities 1 and 2, there are relations of multiplicity 2 that cannot be generated from relations of multiplicity 1, and relations of any multiplicity can be generated from relations of multiplicities 1, 2, and 3."

As written: This was actually all empirical, known worldwide, so to speak, and thus belonged to the global "cultural heritage."

But then the following happened: during the 9th century BC, a writing system developed in the Mediterranean region based on the Phoenician alphabet, which implemented a groundbreaking innovation. The written symbols no longer resembled what they represented, but rather the spoken word. The sound of the language was written down! This had far-reaching consequences that continue to this day, because it made it possible to "materialize" SPOKEN language and thus give it a completely new power. The innovative aspect of this new recording method compared to the older "pictorial scripts" is that it required far fewer symbols and allowed for faster writing. A side effect that was only noticed later was that the language now "written down" in alphabetical script no longer allowed the meaning to be directly recognized in pictorial form. Language written down in phonetic alphabetical script had crossed the so-called "cognitive threshold"! But more on that later.

This resulted in a kind of "armed" spoken language: if you don't smash a "speaking" stone tablet or even grind it completely to dust, you may still be able to reconstruct the

text on it. What "weaponry" does the spoken word alone have at its disposal? Only the testimony of a THIRD PARTY (an "other"). But what is the value of a verbal agreement compared to a written contract, for example, if all the witnesses involved have died?

It gets interesting: What happens when someone writes down how everything should work, and the other person claims that their experience is completely different?

This happened in the Middle Ages and has something to do with the law. The "recorders" simply claimed that what was written in their books was "reality" because their truths could be justified "rationally" in a universally valid way. The other party, the "feelers," countered that "it seems unlikely that people could ever use the same term twice and understand it in exactly the same way," as Martin Siefkes put it. Every word is actually a "proper name" whose meaning is based only on the deepest and most intimate individual EXPERIENCE. This group was called the "nominalists."

It quickly becomes clear that this dispute cannot be resolved, since the deepest essence of human beings is precisely that of being consciousness in a living organism, meaning that our rationality is inextricably embedded in our bodies. The American neuroscientist and anthropologist Terrence Deacon found a plausible explanation for this principle. He called it the "cognitive threshold." In extremely simplified terms, the model could be explained as follows: our organism functions "analogically" and consciousness "digitally," whereby "digital" (digit = number; represented by numbers) in this case should be generalized as "represented by symbols."

In order to represent something with symbols, it is essential to make distinctions as to which symbol should be used for which "thing." But even recognizing a "thing" in the first place means having made a distinction (see "rainbow"), for example, whether it is in front of or behind me, to the right or left, etc. The "three-dimensional space of experience" comes into play. And it is clear that this "space" can only arise AFTER the very first distinction has been made by a "consciousness," that is, after a "firstness" — something completely unknown until now -> an ABSOLUTE OTHERNESS — has appeared and, at that very moment, is transformed into "secondness" — that which can be distinguished. But since a distinction now exists, "the determinant of the distinction" also exists, and this "determinant" is ABSOLUTELY DIFFERENT from that which it "distinguishes"! What is the root of the difference between "thirdness" and "secondness"?

Psst, quick spoiler alert: A "reversal" of the triad has just taken place!

In the "firstness" of its ABSOLUTE OTHERNESS, which — upon crossing the cognitive threshold (at the moment of experiencing it AS conscious experience) — immediately unfolds into a secondness of DISTINCTION between space and time and at the same

time makes us aware of the "thirdness" of the "determinant of the distinction", which leads back to "firstness," since it is always associated with a surprise when the separating factor suddenly and unexpectedly proves to be SIMULTANEOUSLY "absolutely different" and "absolutely connecting".

Psst, quick spoiler: At this moment, the "firstness" is located precisely ON the "cognitive threshold"! We humans, as ambivalent "living beings with consciousness," can only FEEL this situation, but it was precisely this feeling, in this surprising moment of realization, that was once called "revelation." I call it the "grounding moment of symbol formation."

We owe such a "tipping point" once again to the addition of the surprising moment of "firstness" to "secondness." I call this situation a "grounding" moment: when a triadic orbit is completed, when one of its revolutions has led to a SURPRISING experience...

Charles Sanders Peirce can be credited with the enormous achievement of having "rediscovered" this ingenious idea of the triadic, because he recognized that the three "organs" of the triad can represent three fundamental "universes of experience" for humans: "the universe of firstness": the experience of surprise, "the universe of secondness": the experience of opposition, and "the universe of thirdness": ... is somewhat more complicated to explain. Peirce himself found this example, among others: „*Very well. It is highly proper that Secondness should be searched to its very bottom. Thus only can the indispensibleness and irreducibility of thirdness be made out, although for him who has the mind to grasp it, it is sufficient to say that no branching of a line can result from putting one line on the end of another.*“

The fact that the three "organs" of the triad are "swirled" together in rotation can also be seen, for example, in the relationship between "secondness" and "thirdness": the "third" is the "determinant of the distinction" between the "either" and the "or," that which "makes the difference." At the same time, it connects the two binary poles. It creates both distance and connection. This is why chaos theory has now established the idea that every distinction is a "folding," not a zipper, since the three (!) elements of a distinction can never be separated from each other: there is always "the one," "the other," and "the determinant of the distinction."

The idea of the triad is not about "counting to three," but rather about following your mind as it considers what thoughts come to mind about how three things can relate to each other. The most important thing about the structure of the triad is that it allows us to learn what "relationship" actually is, because one of the most common interpretations of "relationship" in our culture today is that a relationship is only a relationship between TWO things. But this view excludes the third. This is a toxic habit of

our "modern Western civilization" that creates the "polarization" and radicalization that are currently threatening our coexistence more and more.

However, the greatest "secret" of the "triad" is that although its internal connections can be recognized in the mind, they cannot be fully conveyed in any language. Everyone "experiences" their own experiences when thinking about any triadic structure. However, they cannot convey this to another person with words alone, just as a verbal description of the Mona Lisa painting cannot replace a visit to the Louvre and the individual experience that comes with it. It is this capacity for ambivalence that defines humanity. Humans possess a triadic nature — Peirce called this characteristic more specifically "teridentity."

What is fatal about our "Western present" is that European civilization has simply forgotten the significance of the triadic. In the medieval "universalism dispute," the "realists" prevailed with their books because both the emperor and the pope legitimized themselves through Roman traditions, and it was therefore believed that Roman law was the best law, since Rome had come so far. And this "Roman law" consisted specifically of late antique manuscripts of a law code enacted by the Eastern Roman Emperor Justinian I, which found its way to Bologna. As a result of studying these texts, "perhaps the oldest university in the world" (self-description) was founded there at the end of the 11th century. And what was the first thing they did there? They interpreted the Roman writings in order to train a completely new profession: that of academically trained lawyers!

It is common knowledge what it feels like to face a lawyer in "unarmed language" — that is, without having anything written down. It was therefore clear that the legal interpretation of "reality" would have a great career in our Western civilization. But what collateral damage did this "novel," "legal," and "rational" interpretation of "reality" cause?

This can be easily understood using the principle of "similarity" (and the related concept of "equality"): From a legal and rational perspective, something is similar if it can be made COMPARABLE on the basis of describable characteristics. EXPERIENCED in the moment similarity is what I — and only I, perhaps even at this very moment and in this mood, based on my life experiences — feel to be "similar."

Perhaps, however, this makes it easier to understand the significance of the quantum mechanical revolution, because it becomes clear that neither the "realists" nor the "nominalists" can emerge victorious from this dispute over "reality".

The only possible "winner" from this situation is the Return of the idea — and it is returning very powerfully, for example through "biosemiotics" — that humans can ONLY AND EXCLUSIVELY be thought of as a "triad." And the experienced miracle of the rotation of a "triad" can neither be "described" in its full emotional quality nor can it be "digitized."